

Supporting Information

Perylenediimide-Incorporated Covalent Triazine Framework: A Highly Conductive Carbon Support for Copper Single-Atom Catalyst in Electrocatalytic CO₂ Conversion

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Fig. S1. BET surface analysis of CTF-Cu-SACs. N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherm of CTF-900 (a) and CTF-Cu-900 (b). Insets show the pore size distribution of CTF-900 (a) and CTF-Cu-900 (b).

Fig. S2. Raman spectrum of CTF-Cu-900

Fig. S3 Surface composition of CTF-Cu-SACs. XPS survey spectra of CTF-900 (a), CTF-Cu-900 (b), and CTF-Cu-N-900 (c). Respective XPS high-resolution C1s spectra of CTF-900 (d), CTF-Cu-900 (e), and CTF-Cu-N-900 (f). (g) XPS high-resolution N1s spectrum of CTF-900.

Fig. S4. FE-SEM images of CTF-900 (a) and CTF-Cu-900 (b) show foam-like structures.

Fig. S5. SEM-EDS mapping of CTF-Cu-N-900. (a) SEM image of CTF-Cu-N-900. Elemental mapping shows the presence of carbon (b), oxygen (c), nitrogen (d) and copper (e) atoms. Inset shows the respective EDS spectra (f).

Fig. S6 HAAD-STEM image of CTF-Cu-N-900 at lower **(a)** and higher **(b)** magnifications.

Table S1. Electrocatalytic performances of Cu-based catalysts for the production of methanol

S. No	Catalysts	Applied potentials	Current density	^a FE of CH ₃ OH	Reference
1	Cu ₂ O/ZnO	-1.3 V vs. Ag/AgCl	-	17.7%	1
2	Pd ₈₃ Cu ₁₇ aerogel	0.2 V vs. RHE	31.8 mA/cm ⁻²	80%	2
3	CuS nanocrystals	0.2 V vs. RHE	41.5 mA/cm ⁻²	77.6%	3
4	CuSAs/TCNFs	-0.9 V vs. RHE	-119 mA/cm ⁻²	44%	4
5	CTF-Cu-SACs	0.2 V vs. RHE	-11 mA/cm ⁻²	72.6%	This work

^aFaradaic efficiency

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